

Home & Abroad

THE REBUILDING ISSUE

2021 - 2022

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HISTORY AND VISION

Home & Abroad was founded in 2014 by two second-year medical students: Aloysus Lawong & Jie Yao. Upon matriculating, Aloysus observed that countless, commendable global health ventures were being undertaken by students and faculty alike at UTSW. Armed with the conviction that these burgeoning global health enthusiasts make up the fabric of a growing and interdependent health community at “Home” and “Abroad,” together they went to work. With the endorsement and support of colleagues and the backing of the Office of Global Health and UTSW leadership, Home & Abroad was born. Our mission is to provide a varied perspective on global and national health endeavors and highlight initiative and achievements by the student body, faculty and friends. Our vision is to become the premier literary forum on campus, utilizing multidisciplinary approaches to address challenges in global and national medicine by providing our readers insightful and accurate information on pertinent global health topics.

SPECIAL THANKS

To Victoria McNamara and Erica Asante from the Office of Global Health for your tremendous help in making this magazine a reality; and to Dr. Angela Mihalic and Dr. Mary Chang for revisions and final

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Home & Abroad is published by the Home & Abroad magazine staff, a registered student organization. Home & Abroad is not an official publication of UT Southwestern and does not represent the views of the university or its officers.

Dear Reader,

No event in recent memory has highlighted healthcare inequality like the COVID-19 pandemic. Both locally and across the world, healthcare's favoritism for the haves and quiet disregard for the have-nots was brought to light in striking manner over the course of the last two years. Plenty has been said about the shortcomings of developed nations' responses at home and abroad, and yet plenty more remains to be said about equitable resource sharing and risk management on a global level. Underlying the entire discussion is the concept of fundamental humanity: how we choose to partition healthcare speaks volumes about who we deem worthy of inclusion in the human sphere and all the benefits of such a membership.

The COVID-19 pandemic has defined a new era in healthcare and social interaction. Though we are still living through this crisis, we have reached a critical vantage point from which we can look back on our response and start to plan a path forward. Whether life returns to one reminiscent of a time before COVID, or we begin to settle into the "new normal", we must look to the future and learn to rebuild what has been lost. Division and inequality cannot be the legacy of our crusade against this disease, or we risk forfeiting our compassion, the most precious resource and weapon against suffering. We hope you enjoy, and that the articles in this magazine inspire you to take up the mantle of global equality.

Parker Davis
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Culture Clash

A Diverse World Responds to the COVID-19 Pandemic

BY STEVEN DUNCAN

Can culture kill? Over the past two years, numerous studies published in the field of cultural psychology have outlined how different value orientations can influence individual and public responses to the ongoing pandemic.^{1,2} Culture can define what is socially responsible behavior.³ A person's cultural environment can also influence how well they handle stress.⁴ Fundamental differences in cultural background and political ideology have a significant effect on preventive behavior such as social distancing, mask wearing, and vaccination rates. Consequently, the toll of hospitalizations and death has varied widely, sometimes with paradoxically worse outcomes in regions with more resources.^{2,5}

East and West

Globally, the unequal impact of COVID-19 has been shaped by differences between Eastern and Western cultures. Nations within Asia and the Middle East responded in distinct ways compared with North America and Europe.⁶ Many experts attribute disparities to Eastern collectivism versus Western individualism. Early in the pandemic, Germany served as an interesting illustration of this division. Although modern-day Germany has been unified by a common political and economic system since 1990, the more individualistic Western Germany experienced a much

higher number of reported cases per capita (up to five times higher) than formerly communist, collectivist Eastern Germany did.⁵

In the West, individualism and personal control have been historically emphasized, whereas Eastern cultures have embraced adjustment and acceptance.⁷ In Western egalitarian societies, leadership is seen as equal to the governed body and can therefore be questioned and dismissed, leading to lower compliance and subsequently faster viral spread. Eastern hierarchical societies are more likely to impose strict measures with greater compliance by the public.² During the first year of the pandemic, strong collectivistic values and low levels of egalitarianism ultimately kept more people alive in the East.⁸

In a study that compared East Asians to Western Europeans, reactions to the threat of infection were also seemingly contingent on differing cultural schemas of happiness; Europeans prioritized personal pleasure via travel and participation in the economy while Asians typically sought social harmony and protection of their local community.⁹ Individualistic groups were more threatened by a loss of autonomy resulting from pandemic-related restrictions, whereas collectivistic groups were more alarmed by potential loss of connection from their support groups.⁴

Individualism and collectivism can

shape the way that people interact with healthcare. Americans are more likely to distrust and blame the healthcare system at large (primary control seeking), while East Asians are more likely to blame an individual doctor for a bad outcome (secondary control seeking). This dynamic has led to slander of political and public health officials in the United States and disproportionately more violence against doctors in China.¹⁰ The novel coronavirus spread rapidly through Western nursing homes in the early days of the pandemic, which was also partly a cultural phenomenon. Individualistic cultures are more likely to place elderly family members in outside facilities, whereas collectivistic cultures generally provide primary caregiving in the home.¹¹

Masks were compatible with East Asian culture, as evidenced by their popularity even decades prior to the pandemic.¹² On the other hand, Westerners had to adjust to this change. In Japan, mask wearing brought relief from anxiety, and people reported wearing masks for this psychosocial benefit regardless of any expectation of risk reduction.¹³ Areas with historical exposure to other pathogenic outbreaks tended to be more culturally prepared to face COVID-19, because they had lower levels of extraversion and were generally more collectivistic and conforming.¹⁴

Other Ideological Factors

Religiosity has been characterized as a double-edged sword in pandemic response. On one hand, physical gatherings drive up the risk of infection. On the other hand, community resources and spirituality are important components of stress regulation and connectedness.¹⁵ Research shows that church attendance and self-reported religiosity are associated with lower

cortisol levels.¹⁶ Religion can also affect social standing. In Malaysia, practicing Muslims were more aware of COVID-19 news simply because they spoke the dominant language, unlike religious minorities.¹⁵

Uncertainty avoidance, a cultural intolerance toward unpredictability, is associated with resistance to change. Because change and adaptability are necessary features of a successful pandemic response, cultures with high uncertainty avoidance are at a disadvantage. Discomfort from uncertainty involves a component of risk aversion, while the resultant fear of change ironically increases risk. High uncertainty avoidance is observed in bureaucratic countries throughout Southern and Eastern Europe. Northern European countries are less avoidant of uncertainty and more willing to adjust to the pandemic. This led to more cooperative behavior, lower odds of testing positive, and a lower mortality risk.¹¹

Cultural preference for time orientations is also important in shaping individual and communal motivations. For example, in East Asian and Europe, people may forgo short-term solutions in favor of addressing future problems. African, Islamic, and American countries are more motivated to deal with acute, immediate crises in the short term but may struggle to manage issues downstream. Long-term oriented countries had a slightly higher mortality rate in the early phases of the pandemic when immediate action was required.¹¹ Longitudinal outcomes remain to be seen.

American Partisanship

Within the United States, liberal and conservative groups have held

significantly different attitudes toward the implementation of public health measures, which continually impacts the progression of coronavirus cases. Cultural and political belief systems can be propagated through popular media and may be mutually reinforcing in their transmission of attitudes about COVID-19. In general, perceived severity of the threat of COVID-19 and perceived benefit of complying with restrictions is positively associated with engaging in preventive behaviors.¹⁷

Studies suggest that health behavior is highly partisan.¹⁸ Though the United States may be considered an individualistic country overall, liberals skew more collectivistic when compared with conservatives.¹⁸ Conservatism is linked with unfavorable views of mask wearing and lower mask usage.¹⁹ For individuals who are resistant to cooperate with recommended public health measures, eschewing masks and vaccines often represents an act of defiance: a statement that the government cannot control what they do.²⁰ Unfortunately, it is not uncommon for people to pay for the political last word with their lives.

In the American South, mask wearing can be viewed as weak within the predominating 'honor culture' (a shared belief in self-reliance and performing toughness to signal the ability to defend oneself). In other states where public health regulations are tighter and collective interdependence is more emphasized, mask wearing can be seen as a civic duty.¹⁹ Social distancing and vaccination are similarly shaped by political and sociocultural identifiers.

In the US, conspiracy theories led to the spread of misinformation and increased fear which adversely affected the public. People who did not believe in the existence of COVID-19 were more

likely to be super-spreaders. Religiosity and collective narcissism (strong in-group identification and entitlement with substantial hostility toward out-groups) is a predictor of believing in and spreading conspiracy theories. On the other hand, trust and optimism are associated with individual participation in public health efforts.¹⁴

Solutions

Cultural values influence health behaviors, so effective communication and public policy changes should demonstrate cultural awareness. Culture should be considered alongside objective measures such as demographic characteristics and constraints of the health system when designing policy.¹¹ In addition, different countries can learn from each other and promote positive cultural reform to challenge their own blind spots.

People living in egalitarian societies tend to respond to the importance of personal responsibility and a sense of control in protecting oneself and others.² Hierarchical communities respond better to an emphasis on societal integrity and collective welfare.²¹ East Asians may be motivated by filial piety (respect for elders), a trait that positively predicts greater wellbeing in pandemic times.²² Efforts to dispel misinformation may be focused on reaching high-risk groups.

The world is increasingly diverse, and every individual possesses a unique set of sociocultural values. Though targeted interventions are important, various communication approaches should be directed to the public given the heterogeneity of attitudes within any given population. Prosocial and family-oriented framing was just as effective as promoting self-interest among Japanese adults when it came to messages designed to motivate prevention efforts.²³ All in all,

leveraging culture is one more tool in the utility belt of public health leadership to better understand human behavior and protect people – from the virus and from themselves.

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Global Health Faculty Feature:

Dr. Cristina Thomas

Dr. Thomas is an Assistant Professor in the Departments of Internal Medicine and Dermatology. Her clinical and research interests include complex medical dermatology and infectious disease-related dermatology. In this Global Health Faculty Feature, she discusses the origins of her interest in pursuing healthcare around the world and gives advice for those looking to get started in the field.

Could you provide our readers with an overview of your global health work in India?

Dr. Cristina Thomas (CT): I worked at the Institute of Applied Dermatology (IAD) in Kerala, India studying quality of life tools in the lymphatic filariasis population. Lymphatic filariasis is not a deadly condition, but there is significant morbidity associated with it. Thankfully, management techniques exist and some of these were developed at IAD. Quality of life is a frequently used outcome measure in studies on management of this disease, but there is no standardized quality of life tool. While in India, I compared the use of three quality of life tools in the lymphatic filariasis population.

What made you want to work with this community?

CT: As a child, our family used to travel to India every year to visit our extended family. My family lived in an area with a high prevalence of lymphatic filariasis. Seeing these patients in the community not only dealing with the physical disability associated with the lymphatic filariasis but also facing a significant amount of stigmatization struck me as a child. These experiences stayed with me throughout college and medical school and seeing the mental and social repercussions of this disease on patients pushed me to want to study quality of life in lymphatic filariasis.

Were there cultural differences that influenced the way you approached healthcare in this community?

CT: Homeopathy is a traditional form of medicine that is practiced in India. A unique approach that IAD takes is to blend classic “Western” medicine with homeopathic medicine which is much more familiar to patients. In the US, homeopathy and other traditional medical approaches are often looked down upon. Many of these techniques have been used for thousands of years in some cultures, and we need more studies looking at the efficacy of these techniques because many of them are probably effective! While at IAD, I learned about the importance of meeting a patient where they are at in terms of their understanding of medicine and how effective traditional medicine can be in some cases.

Are you able to continue this or other global health projects now, and if so, how do you divide your time?

CT: Unfortunately, I started at UTSW in the fall of 2020, during the pandemic. Because of this, I have not had an opportunity to travel back to India. During residency, however, I did some work on Kaposi’s sarcoma in patients living with HIV in Kenya, and based on some of this work, I have started an HIV Dermatology clinic at ACCESS.

What advice would you have for students who are interested in global health?

CT: Before starting a research project, it is key to have an institution or physician on the ground to partner with. They can provide you with the best insight into how to help the population and will give you honest feedback on your ideas. You can plan all you want beforehand, but if something is just not feasible at the location, your planning is for nothing. Your partner on the ground will be key to ensuring your project is effective and beneficial, rather than harmful, to the community.

COVID From a World Unseen

BY AHMED ALSHAIKHSALAMA

Our driver picked us up from the Golden Tulip in Cairo at 2 am sharp. We parked in a long line in front of the Suez Canal, waiting for the military checkpoint to open in the morning. It felt almost like the line to enter Costco on a Saturday morning, except everyone here was going to Gaza. I wondered what could be causing swarms of families to head back to Gaza even at the most dangerous time around the globe. Wasn't Gaza 'an open-air prison'?* At 10 am, I was greeted with a friendly shakedown. My neatly packed bag thrown to the ground and ruffled. Twenty more military checkpoints and 48 hours later, I was at the Rafah border. So far, nothing seemed amiss. 48 hours for a 5-hour journey? ** Check. Military harassment? Check.

After entering Gaza, it was like a portal to a new world. Donkeys shrieked at cars that cut them in traffic. Generations of families lived in one building. We only had 6 hours of electricity a day. Despite the apparent chaos, it was the best time in my life. I visited many generations of my family and met individuals from my parents' stories that I couldn't confirm existed up to that point.

I got around Gaza on rideshare – no not Uber or Lyft. In Gaza, taxis travel

from one suburb to the other. You ride with others going the same direction and will frequently switch between taxis to reach other areas. Since Gaza runs on rideshare, masks were required inside vehicles and were frequently checked by police. Still, the world for Gaza went on as normal. Except nothing about the Gazan experience was normal.

After hearing some concerning news, I went to see our tribe's elder who had come down with COVID. She is 92 years old. The overrun hospitals wouldn't take her. She laid in bed; my tribe circled her, attending to her every need. At one point, she began hallucinating angels. We braced for her final moments.

A few days into my stay, I had the opportunity to meet my recently married cousin Ibrahim. He had done well for himself, becoming one of the most trusted electricians in Gaza, where the unemployment rate hovered over 50% for college graduates. His optimism shined through his face, which was a rare sighting. Many didn't know what future laid ahead for themselves, nonetheless a child. Gaza, like Palestine proper, is an occupied land where families don't know if a child is a blessing or a burden.

Still, I pondered about the slow pace and calmness of everyone I met.

Around the world, it was COVID times. The world was different – chaotic almost – but not for Palestinians; this was just another one of the many challenges they've faced. Their perseverance shined through every hardship in their lives. Car didn't work? Ride a donkey. Electricity out? Use battery generators. Everything had a workaround. Before returning to the US, I received news that our 92-year-old tribe's member made a recovery. She had survived the forceful eviction from her home, living under decades of a restrictive occupation, loss of children and grandchildren from colonizer airstrikes, and even COVID. This is the nature of the Palestinian people. This is what draws us back.

*As described by previous UK prime minister David Cameron, along with other leaders. Search 'Open air prison' on the web.

**48 hours for the journey between Cairo and Gaza is considered 'good' and the route could take up to 2-3 weeks, depending on restrictions.

Vaccine Equity

Reflections and Future Directions

BY PARKER DAVIS

Many events in the last two years have highlighted the realities of global inequality, perhaps none more starkly than the issue of vaccine distribution. Looking back, it is easy to remember a holiday season that felt so full of relief, so full of hope for a future in which the new vaccines would be our saving grace. Yet it is easy to forget that for the vast majority of countries, the very hope—let alone, the reality—of a COVID-free world was many months away. For lower-income countries and those without the healthcare infrastructure of more developed nations, the monumental task of vaccinating entire populations could not begin (and in many cases, still has not begun) without first securing and receiving doses of the vaccine, many of which were locked down by higher-income countries in which the vaccines were produced. Thus, the challenges faced by these lower-income countries were, and continue to be, manifold: they face barriers to possession of doses, barriers to distribution, and barriers to inclusion in a global healthcare crusade.

It is thus no surprise that globally, rates of vaccination are demarcated by national and cultural borders. According to data published by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), rates of vaccination in high-income countries—those falling within the medium-to-high range of the Human Development Index—approach 67%,

whereas rates in low-HDI countries are nearer 10%.¹ But measurements of vaccination rates only begin to scratch the surface of vaccine inequality. The cost of the vaccines constitutes a significant financial burden, especially for lower-income countries. Data compiled by Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance, and UNICEF estimate the cost per COVID vaccine dose (for EUA- and FDA-approved vaccines) to be between \$2 and \$40. This makes the average cost to vaccinate an individual with two doses roughly \$3.70.² The average per capita healthcare expenditure for countries of low-HDI status amounts to approximately \$41, meaning that the vaccination effort for these countries accounts for up to 9% of their total per capita healthcare costs. This is an incredible burden that many countries are simply not equipped to handle. Estimates by the UNDP and WHO predict that in order to meet global public health demand, low-income countries may need to increase their healthcare expenditure by as much as 60%, compared to the meager 0.8% increase requisite of higher-income nations.² It is clear that—without financial assistance from developed countries—public health officials in low-HDI nations stand little chance of fulfilling the vaccination standards decreed by their counterparts across the globe.

The immense pressure that the pandemic has placed on low-income countries will only serve to widen the gap between rich and poor. Gavi predicts a global GDP

loss of \$1.2 trillion due to unequal vaccine allocation.³ Data from the Pardee Center shows that in the areas of education, health, and poverty, the damage done by two years of COVID will push tens of millions of people into destitution, disproportionately affecting those in low-income countries.⁴ According to the UNDP, by the year 2030, nearly eight out of every ten people living below the poverty line as a result of COVID-19 will reside in low-HDI countries—in other words, COVID will disproportionately push individuals in the poorest countries below the poverty line. On the low end, this amounts to 40–50 million people.⁵

To overcome the hurdles set before low-income countries, the UNDP has outlined several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) they hope to help countries achieve in the coming years. These goals range from eliminating poverty and hunger to bolstering clean energy and the economy.¹ Through the combined efforts of several global health organizations, the UNDP believes their “SDG Push” will rescue nearly 100 million people from poverty in the next decade, especially in regions such as Africa, Latin America, and the Middle East. Broadly, this effort involves targeted investment in industries and platforms aimed at increasing access not only to healthcare, but also to education; at increasing government efficiency while decreasing government corruption; and at increasing reliance on green

energy. The UNDP hopes that by 2050, as many as 45 countries will have completely eradicated poverty under the guidelines set in the SDG Push. What makes the SDG Push tricky on a global scale is the tailored approach required by each region—what works for one country may not work for their neighbors. As the UNDP acknowledges, this approach to global health necessitates an individualistic mindset and collaboration between various public and private agencies.

Regarding the vaccination effort, a team led by GAVI, the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI), and the World Health Organization (WHO) is paving the way for vaccine equity. The COVID-19 Vaccines Global Access (COVAX) initiative was announced in April 2020 to coordinate the distribution of COVID vaccines, tests, and medications to low-income countries.⁶ With the logistical help of UNICEF, COVAX began distribution in February 2021. By September 2021, they had delivered roughly 200 million vaccine doses to its member nations. Though still short of its distribution goals for 2021, the delivery of over 300 million vaccine doses in December 2021 alone helped propel COVAX's total distribution to over 900 million doses in 144 different countries last year. And while this figure means that millions of people who may have originally been excluded from the vaccination effort had the opportunity to receive the shot, it is still far short of Gavi's 2 billion dose

goal. Increased demand, insufficient fundraising, and a paucity of vaccine doses have prevented Gavi from reaching its goals for 2021. However, the company believes it can make the necessary adjustments to remain on-target in 2022.

Though programs like SDGs and COVAX are steps in the right direction, the global nature of these efforts poses a challenge to their implementation. As noted by public health experts across the globe, many of the endpoints outlined by the UNDP and Gavi remain vague.⁷ It may be argued that this failure to define ultimate goals was intentional and aimed at allowing nations the flexibility to tailor SDGs to match their resources and exact needs. Biermann et al. believe, however, that this open room for interpretation will only lead to a weakened ability to enforce goal-achievement. More than anything, the authors cite global cooperation as the key to success—despite the seemingly individualistic approach taken by the UNDP and others. And in spite of the individualized incentives, it is clear that achievement of SDGs will require cooperation not only between the private and public sectors, but between nations too. To keep participating countries moving toward common goals, the UNDP has included specific governmental goals designed to bridge potential gaps between global and national aspirations. More than anything, successful implementation of SDGs requires an ability to measure real progress. As of yet, the specific

mechanisms of measurement have not been made clear by the UNDP. Without these guidelines, it is unlikely that the public and private organizations charged with executing the SDGs will meet the specific demands of the UNDP. Further, variability in the way countries approach each Goal will inevitably result in slightly different outcomes between nations.

The COVID-19 pandemic has been an incredible burden on people around the globe. The politicization and nationalism surrounding the pandemic—and especially surrounding vaccination—have made gaining the upper hand over the SARS-CoV-2 virus especially challenging. What should be a global effort to eradicate a dangerous disease quickly became a battleground where misinformation and tribalism are the most lethal weapons. Thankfully, organizations like the UN and WHO recognized early on the importance of combating vaccine nationalism to reverse the course of what could have been a rapid and irreversible slide into destitution for many countries. In addition, they have taken the initiative to leverage the fight against COVID into a campaign for the betterment of society that extends beyond public health. These organizations see an opportunity for a better future—one in which equality reigns and everybody is given a fair shot.

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Pursuing Global Health, Locally

BY ABHINAV THUMMALA

The summer before medical school, I participated in rural health camps on the outskirts of Hyderabad, the city in India where most of my family lives. It was a rewarding experience, and I was particularly interested to see global health deployed within a sustainable, mutually enriching infrastructure. A few months later as a first-year medical student at UT Southwestern, I came across the MD with Distinction in Global Health application page. The program combined structured didactics, immersive clinical experiences, and hands-on research to allow me to learn and grow through direct engagement with international communities. As a fresh-faced first-year medical student, working to further improve my community's health outcomes through the program represented a natural next step. I was lucky enough to be accepted into the program, and I quickly started to work on planning a research project in Hyderabad.

The first COVID cases in the United States made news in January, but the virus was nothing more than a fly buzzing in my periphery at the time. I booked my flights, made plans with my grandparents in Hyderabad, and looked forward to practicing my Telugu. Any concern didn't last longer than a few months, but a text from my dad to stop by Kroger for non-perishables suggested the situation was evolving much more rapidly than I expected. All my plans outside of the continental United States were canceled that summer, and subsequent opportunities to participate in global health through the program also failed to materialize. Looking back on my pre-clerkship years, I kept myself in flux, always waiting for the newsletter announcing a reopening of the world. I regret losing those years; instead of acting on the situation and working to find opportunities here in Dallas, I wallowed in what I had lost.

“Whether or not the virus recedes to grant us normalcy, our communities, here and abroad, could use our help.”

plans with my Hyderabad, and to practicing COVID-related seem likely to a few months, my dad to stop non-perishables

The coronavirus pandemic will continue, or it won't. Whether or not the virus recedes to grant us normalcy, our communities, here and abroad, could use our help. Towards this end, I have worked with the Office of Global Health and Dr. Mary Chang to create a list of global health opportunities that you can pursue here, in Dallas.

Refugee Services of Texas: Dallas

The Refugee Services of Texas provide resettlement services to incoming refugees with the goal of integration and self-sufficiency. Volunteers assist with this mission through mentorship and company, English learning, and transportation.

11880 Greenville Ave. Suite 130, Dallas, TX 75243

Tel: 214-821-4883

Email: dallas@rstx.org

Web: rstx.org/locations/dallas.html

International Rescue Committee

The International Rescue Committee is an international organization that provides far-reaching services to tens of millions of people annually. In Dallas, volunteers may assist with transportation and apartment setup as refugees arrive in the city.

6500 Greenville Ave, Suite 500, Dallas TX 75206

Tel: 214-461-9781

Email: VolunteerDallas@Rescue.org

Web: rescue.org/dallas

Volunteer Coordinator: andrea.jameson@rescue.org

Heart House Dallas

Heart House works to provide comprehensive afterschool programs to children of refugees and immigrants in the Vickery Park neighborhood. Volunteers help students with homework, social-emotional learning, and academic-based learning afterschool or during the summer.

8515 Park Lane, #303, Dallas, Texas 75231

Tel: 214-750-7637

Email: volunteer@hearthousedallas.org

Web: hearthousedallas.org

Catholic Charities Dallas Refugee Resettlement Services

Catholic Charities Dallas, or CCD, is a faith-based social service agency originally founded in 1941. The organization provides a variety of services to people in need and offers volunteer opportunities that include structured internships, emergency voicemail transcription, food pantry work.

1421 W. Mockingbird Lane, Dallas TX 75247

Tel: 214-553-9909

Email: volunteer@ccdallas.org,

Web: ccdallas.org/our-services/refugee-services

Human Rights Initiative of North Texas

The Human Rights Initiative provides legal and social support services for clients who have suffered a variety of human rights abuses. Volunteers may provide translation services, mentorship, and office work.

2801 Swiss Ave, Dallas TX 75204

Tel: 214-855-0520

Email: info@hrionline

Web: hrionline.org

Volunteer Director: lfaulkner@hrionline.org

Learn more at: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1GoHqszkt75sfCotRHikoYQecnPwDSuiYRG2ZKvEIMBA/edit?usp=sharing>

The Texas Winter Storm of 2021

Then and Now

BY PARKER KENEE & JADE CALLOWAY

In 2018, I moved from Virginia to Texas to escape the cold. So, when I woke up in Dallas on the morning of February 14th, 2021 and peered outside my bedroom window, I had to make sure I wasn't dreaming. A Winter Wonderland, with snow several inches deep and the morning sun glistening off of the freshly-lain snow—it was...idyllic. But that sentiment would not last long. The winter storm "Uri" had brought with it a wrath unlike any seen by the state of Texas, a state that many, myself included, had assumed was shielded from the severe winter weather that often struck more northern latitudes.

The snow continued to fall, and then came the power outages. Wonder quickly turned to panic as I took stock of what little food we had to eat, all of which required power to prepare. Road conditions made it too dangerous to drive to a grocery store, and anything within walking distance was closed. With scarce food, and our thermostat dipping below 55 degrees, I was relieved when a close friend invited us to stay with her—she had not lost power. With no shortage of heat, wine, good food, and camaraderie, we felt incredibly fortunate, but anxiety still loomed about the state of our apartment and our community. The otherwise welcome week of respite from work and school—not unlike snow days as a school child—was overshadowed by feelings of concern: we did not know when normal life would resume, how others were faring in the storm, or whether our apartment had been ravaged by water damage. We were fortunate to return at the end of the week to an apartment that had not been damaged by the storm Uri, but

hundreds of thousands in Texas were not so lucky.

The winter storm Uri, and its impact on communities in Texas, revealed a severe vulnerability in the way Texas' energy grid was structured. 91.5% of Texas' residents live within areas of the state that receive electricity from the Electrical Reliability Council of Texas (ERCOT).¹ When temperatures in the state plunged far below freezing for over a week as Uri landed, ERCOT—whose electric grid is isolated from the US' Eastern and Western Interconnection—was unable to meet the electric demands of the state, nor was it able to siphon additional electricity from an outside grid to accommodate the increased demand. What happened next put Texas in the news across the country: ERCOT began instituting rolling blackouts across the state, leaving millions of Texans without electricity, running water, or the ability to leave their homes for extended periods of time. At its peak, 4.5 million residents were without power and, in a survey of communities across Texas conducted by the University of Houston, 69% and 49% of residents lost access to electricity and running water, respectively.¹ One critical difference between this division of resources and others in history—as rolling blackouts are not uncommon in times of greater electrical demand—was the sheer amount of time the resources were withheld: the same survey also found that the average reported electricity black out was 42 hours, and the average reported cessation of running water was 52 hours.¹ Historically, major winter storms in Texas forced ERCOT to institute rolling blackouts

in 1989 and 2011, though electricity demands in both instances were able to be managed with blackouts of approximately 45 minutes.² Simply put, the state of Texas was faced with an environmental emergency for which it was severely underprepared.

The healthcare infrastructure of Texas, including hospitals, outpatient care facilities, and nursing homes, was not spared from the wrath of Uri. Large hospital systems train for incidents that can result in extended loss of power, periodically running Normal Power (NP) shutdowns to simulate such scenarios, but systems were burdened by uncharacteristically long shutdowns during winter storm Uri.³ Chambers Health Facility, in Anahuac, Texas, resorted to diverting water stores from wellness pools to be used for disposal of sanitation waste.⁴ The Crosbyton Clinic Hospital, outside Lubbock, Texas, received local nursing home residents at an already over-taxed facility after the nursing home experienced a roof collapse due to the weight of the snow.⁴ The loss of life directly attributed to winter storm Uri was monumental: the Texas Department of State Health Services (TDSHS) estimates 246 individuals died as a direct result of Uri, primarily due to extreme cold exposure (161), exacerbated pre-existing illness (25), motor vehicle accident (22), carbon monoxide (19), fire (10) and fall (9).⁵ Evidently, modern society is still at the will of Mother Nature.

As in the wake of any tragedy, there is opportunity for retrospection after winter storm Uri, to learn from our mistakes and address vulnerabilities. Several ideas have been proposed by industry experts to better prepare Texas for future

environmental events, including increasing the electricity reserve margin, winterizing infrastructure needed for the harvest and distribution of natural gas energy, and increasing reliance on electricity sources that are less vulnerable to such climate extremes.⁶ Additionally, winter storm Uri underscored the need for a more concerted communication system in regions with impending severe debilitation due to natural disasters. Many Texans were not aware of how potentially severe the effects of Winter Storm Uri could be, and a pre-existing plan was not in place to adequately distribute that message.

As Earth's average global surface temperatures climb,⁷ emergencies of environmental extreme will continue, including, paradoxically, more cold-weather emergencies.⁸ On a humanistic level, these incidents of extreme climate can impact individuals in numerous unforeseen ways: asthmatics unable to operate plug-in nebulizers for essential airway treatments, diabetics unable to keep insulin at proper temperatures, and increasing waterborne illness due to inability to purify water sources.⁹ Winter storm Uri will undoubtedly not be the last large-scale environmental emergency, and it would be in our communities' best interest to use the past as we look to the future for strategies to minimize the destruction Mother Nature is capable of.

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Why Pursue a

Perspectives of an MD/MPH Student

Nivi Sriram sits down with MD/MPH candidate Suman Vadlamani to discuss why she chose a degree in public health, and how her interests have enriched her experiences in medicine.

Why did you choose the MD/MPH dual degree program?

Suman Vadlamani (SV): As an undergrad I was a Public Health minor, and I am grateful that it gave me a different perspective on healthcare in the U.S and taught me how to be involved in a community approach. It opened my eyes to a variety of issues I didn't realize affected healthcare: food security, access to reliable transport, consistent electricity and Wi-Fi, and other factors that traditionally lie outside of the realm of traditional healthcare disparity. I chose to do the MD/MPH dual degree program because I wanted to expand on these perspectives on the social and economic determinants of health I learned about as an undergrad. Furthermore, I wanted to increase the weight of my voice in improving these issues, and I wanted to have a larger reach within the community, which I felt this additional degree would give me the ability to do.

Has learning about public health supplemented your medical education, and if so, how?

SV: The most significant manner I have seen my public health education come into play is during Colleges. For my hospital visits, I have only ever been to Parkland, Dallas County's safety net hospital, and as such the patients I have seen come from a variety of socio-economic backgrounds. My background in public health allows me a greater level of appreciation for how the different determinants of health can affect a patient's management. For instance, if a patient has cancer, I am aware of the fact they may struggle to get to their chemotherapy appointments regularly, or they may be struggling to maintain their source of income. Overall, I believe I have a more holistic approach towards patients, which I think greatly supplements my medical education.

Double Degree?

What specific communities are you interested in working with, and are they local or global health-oriented?

SV: I am very interested in women's health, both locally and globally. Women's health from a public health perspective is just starting to gain its own recognition outside of the scope of the OB/GYN medical specialty. For example, despite women being physiological different from men, they are still given many of the treatments and medications tested on and devised for white men. Now that we are more aware of such underlying issues, I am very passionate about being a part of the change for people who identify as female in our DFW community.

What are you doing for the practicum requirement?

SV: For my practicum I'm going to be working at Parkland to conduct qualitative research on flu and COVID-19 vaccination status of pregnant women. In particular, I will collect demographic, socioeconomic and vaccine status of pregnant women who seek care at Parkland from south Dallas and then conduct qualitative interviews to understand what their current ideas are about vaccines, whether they're hesitant to receive them, and what their perceived benefits are. In tandem, I hope to create vaccine promotional materials which will be disseminated at vaccine drives, the goal of which is to promote access and acceptance in the communities we serve.

What advice would you have for students who want to get more involved with communities on a public health scale?

SV: My advice is to not limit themselves by thinking that only political or policy related work is public health. Instead, one can start as small as keeping an eye out for local ways to get involved in the community through volunteering. Some great opportunities are the farm and food pantries at Parkland and Habitat for Humanity. Even one-time events such as food and blood drives are public health initiatives! Another very important factor in healthcare is literacy, something that most of us often overlook. Specifically, for those with proficiency in Spanish, working as a translator in a clinic setting can help break down language barriers, which can be a large hindrance to healthcare equity. This is equally powerful in a written format, and working to translate promotional information into Spanish is another awesome project that may seem small but can have a massive impact. From an educational standpoint, if you are interested in learning more about public health, but you don't want to commit to the dual degree, consider signing up for the new public health elective this fall!

